
Introduction

What is a Deliberative ‘Mini-Public’?

Deliberative mini-publics are institutions for a diverse group of citizens to reason together about an issue of public concern. To facilitate a deliberation, participants are randomly selected to represent all social groups who are concerned by an issue. They are provided with balanced information about the issue, and a trained moderator facilitates an inclusive and civil discussion of opposing views. Key differences between a typical focus group and a deliberative mini-public are presented in the table below.

Process

1. Participants are surveyed about an issue of public concern.
2. A sub sample is recruited for the deliberation. Only deliberating participants receive a policy briefer and a video with information on the issue.
3. Participants are randomly assigned to deliberate in-person or online.
4. The in-person participants are gathered in a venue in order to discuss the issue.
Online participants gather in a virtual room.
5. Participants view the video with balanced information on the issue, representing the information from the sheets they received during recruitment.
6. Trained moderators facilitate a discussion as participants think through what their own individual views and policy preferences should be, as well as their values and interests.
The online discussion is self-moderated with an automated platform.
7. Towards the end of the discussion, the group prepares policy recommendations that will be given to policy-makers. They also vote privately on whether they agree or disagree with the group’s recommendation.
8. In the week following the deliberation, all participants are surveyed about the issue of public concern for a second time.
9. The results of the process are aggregated and presented to decision-makers in a public event.

Key Principles for Organizers

- Impartiality: Providing information without expressing personal interest.
- Balance: Presenting balanced views in the educational video.
- Engagement: Promoting active citizenship.
- Civil dialogue: Discussion and deliberation based on mutual respect.

Focus Group vs. Deliberation

	Focus Group	Deliberation
Recruitment		
<i>Participants</i>	Stakeholders	“Ordinary citizens”
<i>Sample</i>	Convenience	Representative/Inclusive
Session		
<i>Outcome</i>	Shared opinions	Public policy
<i>Groupsize</i>	4-8	8-15
<i>Facilitate</i>	Discussion	Opposing views
Research		
<i>Preparation</i>	Interview guide	Balanced briefing materials
<i>Methodology</i>	Observational	Experimental

The Key Role of the Moderator

The moderators have a key role in the deliberative mini-public. They ensure the fruitful and civil exchange between participants, while they guarantee that all participants have the same chance to talk and letting all points of views emerge. With their help and support the participants can find their voices, discover their views, and build their opinions. The moderators also serve as liaisons between the participants and the organizers.

Summary of Tasks for Deliberation Event

As a moderator, you will:

- verify that attendees are invited participants;
- facilitate the small group discussion;
- provide support for participants to prepare and rank their policy recommendations, which will be given to decision-makers (the method to follow is described below).

Group Sessions

Introductions

- **Start with full attendance:** The session can only be started if everyone is in the room. You will have a checklist to ensure everyone is present. Use your best judgement to decide when it is appropriate to assume that a participant will not attend. Take care to note which participants are missing at the start of the session.
- **Silence mobile devices:** Before starting the session, ask participants to silence their mobiles.
- **Present the rules:** The following guidelines are simple and straightforward. Points 1 through 3 are to ensure that participants feel comfortable sharing their opinions. Point 4 is critical for discussions. There is no need to reach any consensus in this deliberative mini-public. The deliberation is a time for participants to share their opinions, listen to each other, and weigh their own opinions.
 1. No one is expected to be an expert.
 2. Everyone's voice counts.
 3. Respect and listen to each other's opinions.
 4. No consensus is needed; not everyone needs to agree or disagree.
- **Introductions:** Start by having everyone introduce themselves with their name, where they are from and why they came / why they are interested in the topics. NOTE that when you, as the moderator, introduce yourself, just share your name and that's it. The participants do not need to know where you are from or what your current occupation is. They need only know that you are their moderator for the session. We don't want the participants to make any assumptions about you.

Starting the Discussion

- **Present the information video:** Before starting the discussion, show the educational video. Ask if anything in the video was unclear to participants. If participants request it, you may re-watch (parts) of the video. Make a note of any questions for the organizers.
- **Start discussing the topic:** 'Could somebody start by explaining what they think this policy would do and how it might affect us?'
- **No need for agreement:** Again, participants may try to convince others of their opinion, but do not have to agree; all should share their opinion on an equal basis, and listen to the merits and drawbacks of all points of view.
- **Silent participants:** If some people haven't spoken at all on previous topics, you can prompt them to speak first on a new topic.

- **Silence:** Don't be afraid of silence. The group discussion will start a little slow. After introductions and after you have asked some general questions, there may be some silence. Don't worry if there is some silence, someone will eventually talk, just don't let it be you!
- **'What does this mean?':** Often participants may turn to the moderator to ask for clarification or pose a question. As the moderator, remember that you CANNOT share any outside information or share your own opinions. If participants are asking a clarifying question AND the answer is in the briefing materials, you should refer the participant to their sheets. If the answer is not in the sheets/video, then you should REDIRECT the question back to the group. For example, 'Could someone answer this participant's question?'

Observers

Observers are not allowed to attend this particular deliberative mini-public. Moderators should not be burdened with the additional challenge of preventing verbal or non-verbal interventions by observers. If anybody except a participant attempts to join the deliberation at any time, explain to them that this event is only open to the officially selected representatives.

The Briefing Materials

- **Balanced:** Let the participants know that many experts vetted the briefing materials in the information sheets and in the educational video across the spectrum to ensure that the information is balanced. Information sheets and video contain essentially the same information.
- **Refer to the Briefing Materials:** The materials provide arguments for and against the proposals. These arguments will naturally occur throughout the discussion. If they don't, make them emerge by trying to get it out of the group discussion, ('What would someone else think about this issue?') and if that doesn't work, refer to the materials ('The video offered an argument on the other side, what do you think about it?'). The information sheets/video are a guide, which don't have to be followed in detail. They're more like a checklist.
- **Know the Content:** Be aware of the content of the briefing materials, but don't teach them. The moderators are not professors, but the instruments of the deliberation. There will be participants who don't pay attention to the sheets or video at all; the moderators should be able to quickly point to necessary information in case the participants have questions regarding the contents.
- **NO additional information.** Providing additional information beyond the briefing materials is absolutely prohibited. Stick to the content on the sheets/in the video. Do not refer to any outside information or opinions.

During the Discussion

- **Less intervention is better:** The moderators have the power to destroy the continuity and content of the discussion. A good moderator says very little, but stimulates participants to take part.
- **Control frustration:** You can control the participants' frustration. If someone feels not prepared enough to express an opinion on a certain question you can ensure that her/his opinion has the same value as the other's opinions, e.g. by suggesting that their daily life experiences have the same value as the other's arguments.
- **Create the climate:** The aim is to maintain a good atmosphere with mutual respect and the best possible interaction between the participants. Ensure civility and respect and help the participants to discover their voices.
- **Let everyone talk.** Ensure that everyone has the same chance to express her/his opinions. If some learners are dominating the discussion, don't hesitate to interrupt them. If some participants don't talk at all, turn to them and ask them to express their opinions. If somebody talks too much, invite others to talk, like 'let's hear everyone, we should give everybody a chance to talk' or 'thank you for your views, but we need to allow others also to talk'.
- **Off-topic talk:** Some participants might get off-topic. This may be a good time to interrupt them gently, and prompt another participant for their opinion.

- **Ensure balanced opinions to emerge:** Ensure the balance of the discussion; ensure that arguments for both sides get considered. If nobody is arguing against, ask e.g. ‘what do the people against it say?’
- **Do not express your opinion:** The moderator should never convey her/his own viewpoints, not even with an expression of the face to show approval or disapproval.
- **Handling false statements:** If a participant says something that is factually false, the moderator can ask for others’ opinion on the statement, or ask what the educational video says about it (but never say: ‘This is false’, if you correct the participant’s statement, you end up joining the discussion as a participant, which is not your task for this event).
- **Talking to each other:** The participants should not talk to the moderator but to each other.
- **Side conversations:** Limit all side conversations. We only want one group discussion. If participants are talking to each other on the side, you should stop it. This becomes a distraction to everyone in the group.
- **No show of hands:** Do not ask for a show of hands within a group. Do not permit a participant to ask for a show of hands. The ranking/voting on the list of policy recommendations described below should take place confidentially.
- **Stick to the agenda:** your guide should include an agenda. If participants take too much time for a topic, remind them that there are other topics to discuss as well.

Preparing the Policy Recommendations

- **Task:** About 20 minutes prior to the end of the session, ask your group to develop policy recommendations. Inform them that they will privately rank all recommendations by importance in a second step. Only the two most important (most highly ranked) recommendations will be presented to decision-makers.
- **Flip Chart/Whiteboard/Paper:** There may be a flip chart, paper, or white board in the room which you can use to write out the policies, so that all participants can see. This makes the policy recommendations easier to formulate, and later rank.
- **Formulate the policy recommendations together:** The policy recommendations should be results from the discussion. The group can use the policies from the information materials, or formulate their own. Keep track of ideas that come up during the discussion. Make sure that all recommendations are written down and visible to everybody.
- **Phrasing of recommendations:** Encourage participants to fit their policy recommendations into a single, simple sentence, for example starting with: ‘The government should ...’. More complicated recommendations might not be understood by all participants (or policy-makers).
- **Types of recommendations:** Emphasize that policy-makers will only be able to consider recommendations on the topic that has been discussed. Otherwise, all recommendations are valid. They may be more general or specific than the ones in the information materials. That is okay!
- **Group Ranking:** After you have collected and written down all recommendations, ask the group to weigh the relative importance of these recommendation **individually**, using a modified ‘**Borda-count**’:
 1. Ask each participant to **privately** list all recommendations on a piece of paper in the order of importance. You may use letters/numbers to identify the recommendations on the flipchart/board, so that participants do not have to write down entire sentences.
 2. Collect the individual ballots, and take a few minutes to assign points to them. You may ask participants to help you with this procedure—just make sure they cannot identify the rankings of others. For each ballot, the lowest ranked recommendation receives 0 points, the second-lowest 1 point, the third-lowest 2 points, and so on. If all recommendations are listed in some order, the top-ranked recommendation should receive as many points as there are recommendations, minus one. Special cases:
 - Recommendations that the participant did not list all receive 0 points.
 - It follows that ballots which omit recommendations have overall less weight than ballots which list all recommendations.

- If a participant wrote multiple recommendations next to each other (they are tied), note the number of points assigned to the next-lower recommendation, add 0.5 for each of the tied recommendations, and assign that number of points to all tied recommendations.
 - 3. Add up the points for each recommendation, and announce the result to the group.
 - 4. Ask each participant to write on a piece of paper whether they ‘agree’ or ‘disagree’ with the group ranking.
- **Conclusion:** add up and announce the overall rate of agreement with the group ranking.

Prior to Departure

- **Next steps:** The results of the sessions will be presented to relevant stakeholders during an event in Kathmandu, and all participants will be informed about it via text message, should they wish to attend. Ask participants to please respond to the telephone survey that we will administer within a week from the event.
- **Confidentiality:** Remind participants that both the results from the group discussion and their survey responses will be aggregated/anonymized before we present them to policy-makers—there will be no individual or group attributions.
- **Data collection:** Make sure you collect:
 1. **Picture** of all policy recommendations (including those excluded) and agreement (number of yes votes / total votes).
 2. **Original paper sheets** for ranking ballots and votes on agreement with the group ranking.
 3. **Recordings** (video and audio) of the session.
- **Compensation:** All participants receive the same compensation for their time and travel.

TWO-PAGE GUIDE FOR MODERATORS OF THE NEPAL DELIBERATIVE MINI-PUBLIC

Agenda

1. Introduction (10 minutes)

- Start with full attendance, note absentees
- Silent electronic devices
- Rules:
 - a) No one is expected to be an expert
 - b) Everyone's voice counts
 - c) Respect and listen to other's opinions
 - d) No consensus is needed; not everyone needs to agree or disagree.

2. Discussion (75-90 minutes)

- a) Topic 1: Video (5 minutes)
- b) Topic 1: Discussion Policies 1&2 (30 minutes)
- c) Break (5 minutes)
- d) Topic 2: Video (5 minutes)
- e) Topic 2: Discussion Policies 3&4 (30 minutes)
 - Do not express your own opinions/biases
 - Do not take hand polls
 - Do not add outside information
 - Do not correct false statements
 - No need for consensus
 - Ensure balanced opinions
 - Encourage everyone to talk
 - Interrupt people who talk too long
 - Interrupt side conversations/whispering
 - Participants should talk *to each other*, not to you

3. Prepare Policy Recommendations (20-30 minutes)

- a) Distribute paper for recommendations
- b) Collect up to 1 recommendation per participant
- c) Group Discussion: re-phrase recommendations
- d) Private Vote: Ranking (collect)
- e) Group Ranking: Borda Count (→ top 2)
- f) Private Vote: Agreement (collect)
- g) Group Agreement: added number of 'yes' and 'no'
 - May be from the briefer or on the topic in general
 - Votes are confidential

4. Prior to Departure

- Next steps: Telephone survey, event with decision-makers
- Collect data: (1) picture of all recommendations with agreement rate, (2) original votes (ranking, agreement), (3) audio/video recording
- Compensation: All receive equal compensation

Situations: What to Say

Discussion

- **Start:** Could somebody start by explaining what they think this policy would do and how it might affect us?
- **Silence:** *Wait for somebody to speak*
- **Short discussion:** How do you feel about the potential consequences of this policy? What are the 'pros' and 'cons'? Do you think there's anything else that can be said in favor or against this policy?
- **Everyone agrees:** What might people who disagree with you say?
- **Quiet Participant:** Do you agree with the opinion of the other participant, or do you have any questions about the policy?
- **Talkative Participant:** Thank you for sharing your views, maybe we can give somebody else a chance to share?
- **Off-topic:** Thank you, can we hear from the others what they think about (*policy*)?
- **Question:** Could someone answer this participant's question? Is the answer in the policy briefer/video?
- **Unanswered question:** I will relay your question to the organizers.

Prepare Policy Recommendations

- **Topic:** The recommendations should be on the topics we have discussed; they can but do not have to be the ones listed in the policy briefer.
- **Choosing a recommendation:** Which of the policy recommendations we discussed most interested you, and why? Which of the policy recommendations were of least interest to you, and why?
- **New recommendation:** Do you have any recommendations on our topic that were not in the briefer or video? I remember that somebody had a different recommendation earlier?
- **Similar recommendations:** Is there a way we can make the difference between these policy recommendations clearer for policy-makers?
- **Long recommendation/list:** What is the most important or unique part of this recommendation?
- **Consent to re-phrase:** Does the person who wrote this recommendation agree to re-phrase it?
- **Conclude the discussion:** Does everyone agree with how their recommendation is represented in this list?
- **Handling unusual rankings:**
 - Missing recommendations receive zero points. Rankings that miss recommendations have overall fewer points (weight) than rankings that list all recommendations.
 - Points for tied recommendations = points assigned to the next-lower recommendation plus 0.5 times the number of tied recommendations.

Script: Introduction

Thank you all for coming. My name is and I will be your moderator today. If you have any questions about the event, please feel free to ask me. I would like to start by making sure everyone has a copy of the briefing materials and their badges. Also, please make sure your mobiles are off or on silent mode.

PAUSE—Look around to make sure everyone has briefing materials and their badges, and turns their mobiles off/silent.

Before we begin, I would like to share some guidelines for discussion. This event is an opportunity for everyone to learn and I want to encourage everyone to speak freely.

Many of you do not have any prior knowledge or experience with the political issues that we will discuss today. You were selected as representatives because of these different backgrounds. No one is expected to be an expert, and your opinions are equally valuable and important for the discussion. If you have a little more knowledge or experience, please be patient and encourage and listen to those of you with less experience, so that they can learn and share their views as well. Please respect and listen to each other's opinions and try not to interrupt others. Also, no consensus is necessary, not everyone needs to agree or disagree.

You are here to discuss with each other, not with me. I am only here to help you with that, and to make sure that everybody has enough time to speak.

About 20 minutes before the end of this session, you will, as a group, come up with policy recommendations and rank them by importance. Your ranking will be anonymized and given to government stakeholders for consideration. You will have the opportunity to express your agreement or disagreement with this group ranking in a confidential vote, the result of which will also be given to government stakeholders.

This session is also being recorded. The recordings are only used for our researchers to analyze the discussion and not shared with anybody else. The recordings will be anonymized so that there is no way to identify you.

Again, my role is to facilitate your discussion. Let's start by having everyone introduce him or herself. Please tell us your name and why you came to this event, or what you thought when you were invited.

Example: Vote by Participant P1

Rank	Recommendation	Points
1.	C	3
2.	A	2
3.	D	1
4.	B	0

Script: Prepare Policy Recommendations

You can continue the discussion for another 5 minutes, but we should come up with recommendations for policy-makers soon. I am distributing pieces of paper. Please use them to write down **one** policy recommendation. Please try to keep your recommendation to one sentence, and have the sentence start with 'The government should...'. Your recommendations should be related to the topics we discussed today. They can, but do not have to be the same policy recommendations that were listed in the policy briefer.

Let the discussion continue. Check that there is a flipchart, whiteboard, or poster available to list recommendations so that all participants can see them. At the end of the discussion:

Those of you who have a policy recommendation already, please help the others who may have trouble to write down their recommendation.

After collecting the recommendations and writing them somewhere for everyone to see:

We will now discuss your recommendations to see if some of them should be re-phrased or merged together. Afterwards we will rank your recommendations. **Only the two most highly ranked recommendations will be presented to policy-makers.**

Could somebody read the recommendations we have on our list?

Have participants discuss, merge, and re-phrase recommendations. When participants appear satisfied, start the ranking of recommendations by writing symbols or letters next to each recommendation:

Could everyone now please rank all policies on a piece of paper, using the letters we have written here? Start with the letter for the policy that you think is most important, and write it at the top. Then write the letter for the second-most important policy below it. Then the third, and so on. The letter for the least important policy should be written at the bottom.

Collect the sheets, mix them, and then ask participants to help you with the Borda count:

We will now assign points to your rankings to combine them. The lowest policy on your sheet is assigned 0 points, the second-lowest 1 point, the one above it 2 points, and so on. Could some people help me with that?

Example: Borda Count for 3 Votes (P1, P2, P3)

Rank	Recommendation	P1	P2	P3	Total
2.	A	2	1	2	5
4.	B	0	2	1	3
1.	C	3	0	3	6
3.	D	1	3	0	4

In this example, policy recommendations 'C' and 'A' would be recommended to decision-makers.

After assigning and adding up the points for each policy recommendation:

Well done! This is our group's ranking of policy recommendations. The two most important will be presented to decision-makers. Could you write on a piece of paper if you agree (write yes) or disagree (write no) with this ranking?

Add up the number of yes' and no's, and write them next to the policy recommendation ranking.